

RIGHTIFY GHANA
Empower For Better

MEMORANDUM

TO: THE HONOURABLE CHAIRMAN AND MEMBERS, COMMITTEE ON
LEGAL, CONSTITUTIONAL, AND PARLIAMENTARY AFFAIRS,
PARLIAMENT OF GHANA

FROM: RIGHTIFY GHANA

SUBJECT: PROMOTION OF PROPER SEXUAL HUMAN RIGHTS AND GHANAIAN
FAMILY VALUES BILL 2021

DATE: 23RD SEPTEMBER 2021

CC: OFFICE OF THE ATTORNEY-GENERAL

We are thankful to the Committee for the opportunity to submit our contribution on the 'Promotion of Proper Sexual Human Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021.'

Rightify Ghana is a Ghanaian youth-led human rights organisation that works to improve the lives of marginalised population through capacity building, advocacy, reporting and documenting human rights violations, psychosocial support and other services.

Background

The 'Promotion of Proper Sexual Human Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021' was tabled before Parliament on 2nd August 2021 and consequently the Committee for Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs is seeking comments from the public on its content. According to the proponent of the bill, it aims to review parts of the outdated Section 104 of the Criminal Offences Act, 1960 (Act

29) to further criminalise persons who identify as LGBTTTQQIAAP+ (lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, transsexual, queer, questioning, intersex, asexual, ally, pansexual), outlaw advocacy and ban funding for related issues, as well as legalising and regulating therapies they claim will be provided by “approved service providers.”

In 2014 the African Commission on Human and Peoples’ Rights (African Commission) adopted Resolution 275, titled, *‘Resolution on Protection against Violence and other Human Rights Violations against Persons on the basis of their real or imputed Sexual Orientation or Gender Identity.’* Resolution 275 expresses grave concern about increasing violence and other human rights violations, including murder, rape, assault, in respect of persons based on their real or perceived sexual orientation or gender identity. It calls upon states to act for stopping such violence, to ensure that human rights defenders working on the human rights of sexual minorities are free from reprisals and take appropriate measures to ensure adequate remedies are ensured to victims of such violence. Again, the Resolution strongly urges States, including Ghana, *“to end all acts of violence and abuse, whether committed by State or non-state actors, including by enacting and effectively applying appropriate laws prohibiting and punishing all forms of violence including those targeting persons on the basis of their imputed or real sexual orientation or gender identities, ensuring proper investigation and diligent prosecution of perpetrators, and establishing judicial procedures responsive to the needs of victims.”*

Human rights are almost a form of religion in today's world. They are the great ethical yardstick that is used to measure a government's treatment of its people. The attraction of human rights is that they are often thought to exist beyond the determination of specific societies. Thus, they set a universal standard that can be used to judge any society. Human rights provide an acceptable benchmark with which individuals or governments from one part of the world may criticise the norms followed by other governments or cultures.

All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. This very principle of equality enshrined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights has inspired and transformed the lives of many Ghanaians – and continues to give hope to countless more. Guaranteeing the protection of human rights of all Ghanaians are provisions under the Chapter 5 of Ghana’s Constitution, where equality, diversity, human dignity and freedoms including protections from discrimination are protected under Articles 12, 14, 15, 17, 18, 21, 24 and 26.

Based on the non-discriminatory rights and freedoms enshrined in the Constitution and our analysis of the bill, Rightify Ghana has arrived at the conclusion that the bill is not only discriminatory, but it will also promote hate, significantly leave a negative impact on public health, establish a state sponsored torture of persons who identify as LGBTTQQIAAP+, embolden organised criminals whom have for years targeted LGBTQ+ persons for blackmailing and physical harm, as well as deprive targeted populations from enjoying the rights and freedoms protected under the Constitution.

According to a 2016 report by the Human Rights Watch (HRW), Nigeria’s Same Sex Marriage (Prohibition) Act, 2013 (SSMPA) has made a bad situation much worse for Nigeria’s beleaguered lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender (LGBT+) community. Even though the report *“found no evidence that anyone has been prosecuted under the SSMPA, its impact has been far-reaching and severe”* as it *“effectively authorises abuses against LGBT people.”*

Even though Ghana has not passed laws such as the SSMPA, a 2018 Human Rights Watch report documented the human rights impact of Section 104(1)(b) of the 1960 Criminal Offences Act (Act 29) on the lives of LGBT+ people in Ghana. The report concluded that *“despite the rare, if any, prosecutions under this provision, Human Rights Watch found that the criminalisation of adult consensual same-sex conduct contributes to a climate in which violence and discrimination against LGBT+ people is common.”* Again in 2018, the UN Special Rapporteur on extreme poverty and human rights, Phillip Alston, also expressed concern about how stigma and discrimination against LGBT+ people undermine their ability to

find meaningful work. He spotlighted LGBT+ poverty in Ghana, stating how persons are routinely discriminated against in the job market. A recent HRW investigation detailed shocking human rights violations suffered by the 21 persons who were arrested and detained in Ho this year. According to the report, detainees suffered cruel and degrading treatments including checking and taking photographs of an intersex person, whom the police also threatened to urge other inmates to rape. These are just a few of the many worrying problems that the bill will not only worsen, but also create new ones.

Rightify Ghana does not support the *'Promotion of Proper Sexual Human Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021'*. We submit this memorandum in part to urge Parliament to reject the bill but, principally, to highlight its far-reaching vicious implications on human rights, public health, the economy and academic research through a systematic clause-by-clause analysis, as well as make recommendations on legislations that will protect sexual minorities from violence and human rights violations to ensure that all Ghanaians fully enjoy freedom and justice.

Clause-wise analysis and suggestions

Application and Interpretation

If adopted by parliament, Clause 1 of the draft *'Promotion of Proper Sexual Human Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021'* intends to target and criminalise persons who “holds out” as LGBTTTQQIAAP+, engages in sexual activity the bill also seeks to outlaw as well as persons who provide or participate in gender affirming surgeries. The Clause 2 provides some definitions to distinguish persons intended to be criminalised under the draft bill. In contrast, the Article 17 (2) of the Constitution of Ghana states that “A person shall not be discriminated against on grounds of gender, race, colour, ethnic origin, religion, creed or social or economic status.” The Constitution promotes “equality and freedoms from discrimination,” even though the bill narrows the definition of “gender.”

In addition, the Article 2 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) states that “Everyone is entitled to all the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration, without distinction of any kind, such as race, colour, sex, language,

religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status. Furthermore, no distinction shall be made on the basis of the political, jurisdictional or international status of the country or territory to which a person belongs, whether it be independent, trust, non-self-governing or under any other limitation of sovereignty.” While the argument linking LGBTI+ persons to “*other status*” is often disputed, this link has been made in applying key international documents such as the UDHR, as well as legally binding international treaties like the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights. The term *other status* is meant to have a flexible application and capture the experience of social groups that are vulnerable, have suffered, and continue to suffer marginalisation. This presence of “*other status*” promotes diversity and inclusiveness, where it represents other identities including sexual orientation, gender identity and expression, and sex characteristics (SOGIESC). We encourage the Parliament of Ghana to reject these Clauses.

Duty to promote proper human sexual rights and Ghanaian family values

It is alarming that Clause 3 of the draft ‘*Promotion of Proper Sexual Human Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021*’ places a major responsibility on citizens, some personalities, State and non-state institutions to promote the bill. Subclauses (3)(a)(b) and (c) also seek to nationalise and impose a responsibility on the State to integrate the so-called proper sexual human rights and Ghanaian values “*into the fabric of national life*”, introduce them into “*relevant aspect of national planning*” and ensure that they are “*adopted and developed as an integral part of the growing needs of society.*”

Leaving no one behind lies at the heart of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. This principle is mentioned at least seven times in the Agenda itself, and has been a recurrent theme in documents, pledges, call to actions, interventions and statements delivered since - by Member States, the UN and civil society. A clear commitment to inclusiveness is made in the text of the Agenda when Member States “*pledge that no one will be left behind*” while at the same time

recognising that the dignity of the human person is fundamental, and by pledging that all goals and targets be met for all nations, peoples and societies committing to also reach those furthest behind.

However, despite the frequent use and reference to this principle, focused efforts to leave no one behind already remain insufficient in Ghana, in terms of policy design, implementation and review. The basis for the inclusion of LGBTI+ persons within the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is captured by the design of the goals themselves as well as the formal international treaties and resolutions they are built on. First and foremost, the SDGs are grounded in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), which posits that “*all human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights.*” Additionally, the United Nations Human Rights Council, whose mission it is to promote and protect human rights around the world, has produced multiple resolutions, such as A/HRC/29/23, 27/23 and 17/19, that explicitly call for the end of discriminatory laws, practices, and acts of violence based on SOGIESC. Within the international human rights community, a panel of international experts also published the Yogyakarta principles to both serve as a universal guide to the human rights of LGBTI+ persons and outline binding international legal standards with which all States must comply, including the right to legal recognition and freedom from torture.

Moving to the goals themselves, SDG 10 focuses on reducing inequalities within and among countries. Target 10.2 states that “*by 2030, empower and promote the social economic and political inclusion of all, irrespective of age, sex...or other status,*” a classification that is commonly interpreted as including LGBTI+ persons. In Ghana’s effort to reduce inequalities as part of actions to reach the SDGs, where no one is left behind, we appeal to the Parliament of Ghana to reject Clause 3 which seeks to undermine our democracy and exclude LGBTQI+ issues in the country’s policy development and implementation.

Prohibition against undermining proper sexual human rights and Ghanaian family values

It is worrying that Clause 4 of the proposed bill intends to suppress dissent in subclause (1)(a) and (b), where it prohibits undermining the proposed legislation “*directly or indirectly, instigate, command, counsel, procure, solicit, or in any other*

manner purposely aid, facilitate, encourage or promote, whether by a personal act or presence or otherwise, an act...” This provision is unconstitutional. Contrary to Clause 4, Article 21 of the Constitution of Ghana guarantees all persons some freedoms. For example, the (1)(a) and (1)(b) of the Article protect the “*freedom of speech and expression, which shall include freedom of the press and other media*” and “*freedom of thought, conscience and belief, which shall include academic freedom*” respectively. Ghana prides itself as upholding democratic principles, constitutional rule and civil liberties, therefore, we suggest that Clause 4 should be omitted by Parliament.

Duty to report

A noteworthy fact to pay attention to is the situation where most LGBTQ+ issues in Ghana end up with no evidence of crime, because most reported situations are based on suspicion as it is uncommon to see persons who identify as part of the community engaging in sexual activities publicly, and therefore do not pose any harm or threat to others. However, it is disturbing that Clause 5 of the draft bill is imposing a duty to report on citizens. This is needless and may aggravate the climate of fear, encourage arbitrary arrests and extrajudicial crimes including blackmail and torture, which are some of the human rights violations already being experienced by this vulnerable population. The Clause may lead to the deprivation of *personal liberty, respect for human dignity* as well as *equality and freedom from discrimination* as protected under Articles 14, 15 and 17 of the Constitution of Ghana. The suggestion to Parliament, therefore, is for this Clause to be omitted.

Prohibition of LGBTTQQIAAP+ and related activities

The Clause 6 of the draft ‘*Promotion of Proper Sexual Human Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021*’ disingenuously related LGBTTQQIAAP+ sexual ‘activities’ to bestiality. This is deceitful because even the Clauses 1 and 2 where the draft detailed the bill’s Application and Interpretation, there was no mention of an identity of persons who engage in sexual activities with animals. In addition, the Section 104 of the 1960 Criminal Offences Act (Act 29) is not the creation of Ghanaian heritage and values, but rather a colonial import. Citing a negative

colonial legacy, the Section 104 of Act 29, as an inspiration in drafting the far-reaching bill to criminalise sexual activities between consenting adults and to promote discrimination, inequality and torture is against the spirit of the preamble of the Constitution, in addition to several fundamental rights set out in the Constitution and various provisions of international law. As such, we plead with Parliament to reject Clause 6.

Procuration, detention with intent to commit prohibited sexual activity, and keeping a brothel for a prohibited sexual activity

It is common knowledge that people who do not like LGBTQI+ people are more likely to use fear, falsehood, misinformation and prejudice to promote hate against the already marginalised population. Clauses 7, 8 and 9 intends to associate the targeted persons to procuration and detaining others for sexual activities, as well as prosecute owners of accommodation spaces who grant access to LGBTQI+ persons. These Clauses are purposeless, as the Criminal Offences Act has Sections 97 through 111 dealing matters of *consent* and *procuration* including *rape*, and Section 277 also focusing on issues of *brothel*. For example, if a sexual activity is found to be procuration or detention with intent to commit prohibited sexual activity, the existing laws in the Criminal Offences Act can be utilised. We request the Parliament of Ghana to reject these Clauses which may create duplicity.

Prohibition of gross indecency

Within Ghana's Criminal Offences Act is Section 278 that tackles *gross indecency* and states that "*whoever publicly and wilfully commits any grossly indecent act is guilty of a misdemeanour.*" The Clause 10 of the draft '*Promotion of Proper Sexual Human Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021*' which classify "*public show of amorous relations*" between or among persons of the same sex and persons who have "*undergone gender or sex reassignment,*" as well as "*intentional cross-dressing to portray that the person is of a gender different from the gender assigned at birth...*" as "*grossly indecent acts,*" do not present the harm or threat such activities pose to others. Gross indecency is already criminalised in the Criminal Offences Act,

therefore, the duplicitous intent to add it to the proposed bill should not be overlooked. Considerately, Clause 10 should be omitted by Parliament.

Void marriage

Where Clause 11 purports to criminalise marriage between persons of the same sex or person who has undergone gender and sex reassignment, it attempts to suggest legislation for a non-existent problem. The Sections 262 through 272 of the Criminal Offenses Act and the Marriage Act make provisions for dealing with marriage matters in Ghana. Therefore, we urge the Parliament of Ghana to reject Clause 11.

Prohibition of propaganda of, promotion of and advocacy for activities prohibited under this Act; prohibition of propaganda of, promotion of and advocacy for activities directed at a child

The Clauses 12 and 13 have intention to censor information about LGBTQ+ people's lives - presenting homosexuality as being a norm in society - under the argument that it contradicts Ghanaian family values. This includes, but is not limited to, information provided through the press, television, radio, social media and other internet platforms. First, the Article 21 (1)(a) of the Constitution of Ghana protects "*freedom of speech and expression, which shall include freedom of the press and other media*" and thus all persons can express their unpopular opinions on both traditional and new media without facing backlash or consequences.

Advocacy seeks to ensure that all people in society can: have their voice heard on issues that are important to them, protect and promote their rights, have their views and wishes genuinely considered when decisions are being made about their lives. As Ghanaian citizens, LGBTQ+ persons and their allies are indispensable part of our democratic system and advocating for better treatment as well as calling for change in laws to protect them are not against the Constitution. Also, the Article 162 (1) of the Constitution also states that the "*freedom and independence of the media are hereby guaranteed*" and Section (2) of the Article adds that "*subject to this Constitution and any other law not inconsistent with this Constitution, there shall be no censorship in Ghana.*" The Constitution emphatically discourages all

forms of *censorship*. Even under circumstances where the Article 164 of the Constitution limits rights and freedoms, it also guarantees “...*the Purpose of protecting the reputations, rights and freedoms of other persons.*” Consequently, we call on Parliament to omit Clauses 12 and 13.

Prohibition of funding or sponsorship for prohibited activities

With an intention to outlaw funding and sponsorship, Clause 14 of the proposed bill does not only target LGBTQ+ individuals but human rights defenders including organisations who offer needed services to the vulnerable population. The Declaration on the right and responsibility of individuals, groups and organs of society to promote and defend universally recognised human rights and fundamental freedoms (hereafter Declaration on Human Rights Defenders) adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 1998 explicitly grants human rights defenders the right to access funding.

Article 13 of this Declaration states: “*Everyone has the right, individually and in association with others, to solicit, receive and utilise resources for the express purpose of promoting and protecting human rights and fundamental freedoms through peaceful means, in accordance with Article 3 of the present Declaration*”. It should be noted that while the Declaration on Human Rights Defenders protects the right to solicit, receive and utilise funds, it does not place restrictions on the sources of the funding (public/private, local/foreign). Therefore, it implicitly includes in its scope the right of non-governmental organisations, including human rights defenders to access funds from donors to the same extent as government.

Moreover, the UN Special Rapporteur on the situation of human rights defenders has stressed that access to funding “*is an inherent element of the right to freedom of association*”, and that “*in order for human rights organisations to be able to carry out their activities, it is indispensable that they are able to discharge their functions without any impediments, including funding restrictions.*” The UN urge member States including Ghana to promote and guarantee the right of NGOs to access funding – including foreign funding – as an integral part of their obligation to respect and promote the right to freedom of association, which is protected under

Article 21 (1)(e). An attempt to ban funding and sponsorship to the LGBTQ+ persons as well as human rights defenders is an unfair practice, therefore, Clause 14 may be omitted.

Disbandment and prohibition of LGBTTQQAAP+ group, society, association, club or organisation

Clauses 15 and 16 of the draft *'Promotion of Proper Sexual Human Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021'* intends to not only ban existing LGBTQ+ groups and organisations but make it impossible to form and operate new ones. Civil society organisations play multiple roles. They are an important source of information for both citizens and government. They monitor government policies and actions and hold government accountable. They engage in advocacy and offer alternative policies for government, the private sector and other institutions. They deliver services, especially to the vulnerable and underserved. They defend citizen rights and work to change and uphold social norms and behaviours. For example, UNAIDS dedicated the observation of the 2019 World AIDS Day to communities-led movements because indeed “communities make the difference.” Communities make an invaluable contribution to the AIDS response. The UNAIDS validates that “communities of people living with HIV, of key populations - gay men and other men who have sex with men, people who use drugs, transgender people... - and of women and young people lead and support the delivery of HIV services, defend human rights, support their peers. Communities are the lifeblood of an effective AIDS response and an important pillar of support.”

The African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights' 376 Resolution on the Situation of Human Rights Defenders in Africa - ACHPR/Res.376(LX)2017 calls upon State Parties to “Adopt specific legislative measures to recognise the status of human rights defenders, and protect their rights and the rights of their colleagues and family members, including women human rights defenders and those working on issues such as extractive industries, health and HIV/AIDS, reproductive health, sexual orientation and gender identity, promotion of peace and democracy, fight against terrorism, and respect for human rights” and to “Refrain from using the fight

against terrorism as a pretext to restrict fundamental freedoms, including freedom of religion and conscience, expression, association, assembly and movement.” The right to freedoms of association and assembly, protected under Article 21 of the Constitution, include a right to form and participate in organisations. With the above clearly stated, we request that Parliament may reject these Clauses.

Prohibition of adoption and fosterage for LGBTTQQAAP+ persons

While there is no official records and active debate about the adoption of children by LGBTQ+ people, Clauses 17 and 18 intends to create legislation for an inexistent situation in Ghana. The Children’s Act of Ghana already has provisions made for guiding the process of adoption and fosterage. It clearly details who are eligible to be granted adoption and fosterage orders. We suggest to Parliament that Clauses 17 and 18 may be omitted.

Protection of victims of prohibited sexual activities

We are concerned that Clause 19, which intends to protect victims of sexual activities that the proposed bill also seeks to criminalise, may become the single motivating factor to promote *blackmail* towards LGBTQ+ personal. As a result of *homophobia* and a commonly held believe that LGBTQ+ persons are wealthy, such persons are prone to blackmail. For example, there have been cases where members of this population get trapped by individuals and groups and are threatened to pay large sums of monies or risk being beaten, publicly disgraced or sent to the police backed by fabricated stories. Most people discriminate against LGBT+ people based on suspicion, so if this provision is passed into law, we may see an increase in crimes where criminals target people they suspect to be LGBT+ and blackmail them, because people would rather pay for their freedom than being jailed and made to pay large compensation pay-outs to their alleged victims. Worried that Clause 19 may embolden an existing criminal group to threaten and do more harm, we request that Parliament may reject it.

Access to medical help or treatment by accused, flexible sentencing, assistance for questioning and intersex persons, and regulations

We find it worrying that Clauses 20, 21, 23 and 24 attempts to promote so-called *conversion therapy*. The term refers to the widely discredited practices that attempts to change, 'cure' or 'repair' a person's sexual orientation, gender identity, or gender expression. According to the mental health community and multiple studies, *“there is no scientific evidence published in psychological peer-reviewed journals that conversion therapy is effective”* and *“no longitudinal studies conducted to follow the outcomes for those individuals who have engaged in this type of treatment.”* However, they point out that research consistently shows the harmful effects of the practice including causing *depression, anxiety, self-hatred, social withdrawal and thoughts of suicide*.

The UN Independent Expert on Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity (SOGI) has concluded that conversion therapy amounts to *cruelty, torture, inhumane, or degrading treatment or punishment*. Torture and other forms of cruel, inhumane, or degrading treatment or punishment are unequivocally prohibited, without exception, by the UN Convention against Torture as well as other international and regional human rights instruments. The UN Committee against Torture, the UN Special Rapporteur on Torture, the UN Subcommittee on Prevention of Torture, and the Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) have stated that conversion therapy contravenes the prohibition against torture and other cruel, inhuman, or degrading treatment or punishment. In its 2015 annual report, the OHCHR stressed that states *“have an obligation to protect all persons, including LGBT and intersex persons, from torture and other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment”* and found that conversion therapy breaches this duty.

The UN Convention against Torture and other international and regional human rights instruments not only prohibit torture but oblige states to prevent public authorities from *“directly committing, instigating, inciting, encouraging, acquiescing in or otherwise participating or being complicit in any acts of torture”* and other cruel, inhuman, or degrading treatment or punishment. The proposed bill will institute a *State sanctioned torture and degrading treatment towards LGBTQ+ persons in Ghana*, as it directly tasks the Ministry of Religious Affairs and Culture to liaise with non-existent *“approved service providers”* and consult with the Ministry of

Gender, Children and Social Protection as well as the Ministry of Health to perform other duties the proposed bill also seeks to create. If passed, the implementation of the bill may impose an expenditure on public funds, which breaches Article 108 of Ghana's Constitution. We encourage Parliament to take into consideration the above argument and get Clauses 20, 21, 23 and 24 taken out.

Prohibition of extra judicial treatment

While Clause 22 is laudable because it seeks to protect LGBTQ+ persons from assault, harassment and abuses, it predominantly bears the element of deception and hate. Why does a Clause which supports facts that LGBTQ+ persons are vulnerable to human rights violations including physical harm, classify such cruelty as a "misdemeanour" in Subclause (2)? Also, in Subclause (3) of this Clause of the proposed bill, the use of harmful graphic description to degrade the lives of LGBTQ+ persons "does not constitute abuse, assault and harassment." It seems to ignore the fact that harmful graphic descriptions can be so detrimental to mental health because the images may not be real. This may contribute heavily to discrimination and other human rights violations. We must work to eradicate hate in Ghana. Therefore, we encourage Parliament to reject this Clause.

Consequential amendment

Contrary to Clause 25's intention to amend the Extradition Act, 1960 (Act 22) to get accused LGBTQ+ persons returned to the country, Article 14 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights states that everyone has the right to seek and enjoy asylum from persecution in other countries. Also, the 1951 UN Refugee Convention (and its 1967 Protocol) protects refugees from being returned to countries where they risk being persecuted. In addition, the African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights Resolution 275 "Condemns the increasing incidence of violence and other human rights violations,... arbitrary imprisonment and other forms of persecution of persons on the basis of their imputed or real sexual orientation or gender identity" and particularly "condemns the situation of systematic attacks by State and non-state actors against persons on the basis of their imputed or real

sexual orientation or gender identity.” The attempt to amend the Extradition Act is needless, therefore, Clause 25 may be thrown out.

Recommendation

We must become more inclusive in the way we defend human rights. We deliver a public service in the interest of society, but we do not own that service. We talk about, for and sometimes with people who have suffered human rights violations. But we rarely empower them to speak for themselves. They should take part in decision-making processes as much as possible. We should learn to listen more, and they must have the space to tell their stories and shape the policies and laws that concern them. The following recommendations are based on our analysis of the bill and our engagements with the target population.

1. Adopt protective laws to prohibit discrimination against LGBTQ+ and intersex persons, ban hate crimes and speeches, and make provision to legally recognise gender identity;
2. Ensure discriminatory laws against consensual same-sex relationships are repealed including removing ambiguous, vague, undefined and unsound concepts, such “*unnatural carnal knowledge*”; and
3. Design and pass legislations that encourage policies and programmes to recognise and address the diversity of LGBT+ and intersex people, including with regard to multiple and intersecting forms of discrimination based on such factors as sex, ethnicity, age, religion, poverty, disability, health and others.

Conclusion

When states adopted the Universal Declaration on Human Rights on 10 December 1948, they pledged themselves to achieve equality. Giving practical effect to that vision is still possible – but only if we choose to strengthen freedoms, promote participation and empower all people. Despite progress in many areas over the last decades, people in Ghana are still stigmatised because of their actual or perceived sexual orientation or gender identity. Many lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender and intersex (LGBTI) persons cannot fully enjoy their universal human rights. They run

a risk of becoming victims of hate crime and may not receive protection when attacked in the street by fellow citizens. Our societies already breed divisive levels of inequality, fear and polarisation. The passage of the “Promotion of Proper Sexual Human Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021’ will significantly contribute to hate and torture towards persons who identify as LGBTQI+.